

CURRENT STATUS OF GLOBAL AEROMICROBIOLOGY STUDIES

D. R. Saxena ¹, P.D.Bagade ²and S .A.Awasthi³

1 Retd Professor Zoology KNM Nagpur, 2 School Teacher Nagpur, 3 Lecturer Senior college, Gondia (M.S.); India

H.O.D, Zoology Department, Kamla Nehru Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur (M.S.), India

Abstract:

Climate change when it had commenced due to anthropogenic activities is currently also influencing cells, propagules, environment aerosol borne, bioaerosol borne dispersal of microorganisms (modes like the annual dust storms, urban and metropolitan suspended dust by vehicle plying on roads, desert storms, volcanic eruptions, silica- asbestosis, cement dust from building construction and industries, etc) are the major factors elevating problems like contact dermatitis, respiratory diseases, allergies, occupational hazards (lung cancers, etc) to humans and mammals. Thus, aeromicrobiology is concerned with health status and socioeconomic progress of humans globally. Several species of aspergillus spores cause skin and respiratory tract infection. *A. niger* and *A. fumigatus* is the cause of otomycosis due to infections of outer ear canal. Defaecating in open, dessication, and dispersion of faecal contaminated soil carry airborne microorganisms (fungi, bacteria, viruses etc.,) far and wide. Tuberculosis, diphtheria, meningitis, pertusis, *Streptococcus pneumonia* as well as anthrax; Pandemic of Covid-19 and other virus infections spread through air. This is through bioaerosol - aerosol transition facilitated by moisture, heat, temperature and air currents. Moreover, both natural and unnatural factors alter aeromicrobiology impact on humans. A 'solar aeromicrobiology model' to purify air at any place have been proposed to eradicate or reduce pathogenic and non-pathogenic microorganism (proposed by D.R.Saxena).

The rapid Zooplane are "Machzooplane" such as birds, bats, and insects spread all types of microorganisms intracontinentally if they are migratory (also fishes), if not intercontinently. The intracontinental zooplane include above stated animals as well as rodents, reptiles, etc., that daily move in search of food, mate, etc. The slowest but ecologically significant zooplane are bugs, ants, soil worms that disseminate the nonpathogenic and pathogenic microorganisms occurring in air, water as well as soil borne medium. Scavengers also disseminate microorganisms (using various media-animal/human microbial cycle as proposed by the author) due to their feeding- defaecation and locomotory behaviour. Use of AI fabricated and

controlled universal solar aeromicrobiology model also minidomestic models in every residence / flat has been hypothesized. The Prions may be a discarded protein particle of a faulty gene that is quiescent and may be accidentally switched on. Now such genes may metabolically synthesize materials such as DNA, RNA, Proteins, etc., in the bodies of microorganisms, invertebrates and vertebrates including humans. This mechanism may be for slow or rapid evolution of self and non self infectious agents (this unwanted DNA, RNA, Proteins that are accidentally synthesized and are not degraded and now cause diseases), their production may be accelerated manifolds triggered by continuous current climate as well as climate changes in future and that will be the cause of global human deaths.

Keywords: Dust storm, air, microbes, climate change, zooplankton, solar model.

Introduction

There are two domains of aeromicrobiology based on definitions (a) airborne spores of fungi and other microorganisms as well as plant pollen grains (1930 definition) (b) according to Jacobs, 1991) later the definition have incorporated the fungal spores, bacteria, viruses and migrating and dispersing populations of insect species also; D.R. Saxena (2024) views the global climate shift will increase desert dust storms, increase marine water air sprays, volcanic dust, transport vehicle induced spread of dust in rural, semiurban and urban areas especially in the metropolitan cities will favour severe outbreaks of insect pests that act as vectors of above ingredients of aeromicrobiology transit; as well as the bioaerosols as was evident in the spread of covid virus from China leading to global covid 2019 pandemic (air to humans and human lung bioaerosol back to atmosphere defined as the bio-aerosol-virology, (D.R.Saxena 2024). Currently aeromicrobiology studies focus on the microorganism and their propagule transit, through the radionuclides, suspended particulates, pesticides, etc. According to the authors of this review article the environmental pollutants like gases, fumes, ozone, etc., influence the populations of consortium of pathogenic and nonpathogenic microbes.

Research On Aeromicrobiology:

(a) The book Microscopic Examination of Air include systematic research done on fungi in the premises of Calcutta Jails (1878) by Cunningham. Exhaustive studies on rust spores were done by K.C.Mehta from 1942 until 1952 at Agra College in U.P., these funicular propagules infect the wheat and barley as well as other garden plants at an altitude of 2000 meters. Aeolian transmission of rust spores occurs during extreme weather conditions towards the hills from the plains and vice - versa.

Epidemiology Of Fungi Of Agricultural Crops: Several investigations in the past were carried out by workers on aeromycology in different crop fields to unravel mode of spread of pathogenic plant diseases and also to develop an authentic forecasting system; according to authors to alert the growers to employ necessary steps to prevent economic losses. The black and brown rusts of wheat exhibit "hop jump" strategy from hills of South India towards plains of Central India facilitated by storms that originate in the Bay of Bengal in Arabian sea region (Joshi et al., 1972; Nagarajan and Singh 1973). The cloud images captured using GIS technology was used by Nagarjun and Singh (1973) to forecast occurrence and dissemination of *Alternaria*, *Cercospora*, *Helminthosporium*, *Puccinia*, etc., that cause specific fungal diseases and morbid conditions in cereals, fruits and sugarcane agrobios systems. Similarly, 25 dominant airborne fungal infestations in Kurukshetra potato fields were recorded by Navneet (1995 -1996) that proliferate in rainy seasons comprise of *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *A.niger*, *Cladosporium herbarum*, *Epicoccum nigrum*, *Penicillin citrinum*, *P.cyclopium*, etc.

Airborne Dispersion Of Microbes : According to (D.R.Saxena 2024) the bioaerosols emanate from mammals and humans during travel journey and static conditions (sleeping, resting, talking, etc) also by activities such as coughing, spitting, and sneezing and are disseminated by climatic factors like wind, storms (desert, forest, agriculture land), volcanic dust, radionuclide dust, mining dusts, dry faecal dusts, snowfall in polar regions, etc.The floating particles of soil, water vapour, mineral and nonmineral mine particles, hair, fur, faecal, dusts, etc., act as nuclei to shuttle the propagules and microorganisms.Other factors are flowing and static water, soil erosion, and soil dust during construction operations, etc., that release aero - allergens of plant and animal origin (aerozoonotics). Pathogenic aeolianviruses: Influenza viruses A, B and C are RNA Orthomyxoviruses that cause influenza in vertebrates (birds, mammals that are non-human reservoirs) and humans. Highly infectious pleomorphic spherical particles of these viruses are of 80 to 120 nm diameter.

Airborne Dissemination Of Bacteria: Atmosphere is one route of transmission of pathogenic (pneumonia, meningitis, tuberculosis, etc) and nonpathogenic bacteria from environment into the appropriate host for perpetuation that occurs by bioaerosol nuclei of 1.0 - 4.0 um diameter. Non-human vertebrate reservoir bioaerosol liberate anthrax bacterium the *Bacillus anthracis*; inhalation of spores cause anthrax disease (Youmans et al., 1985).Air, dust, sand storm, volcanic dust, etc., are difficult to be totally eliminated. Only indoor filtration or purification of air can be partially done to remove dust and microbes and is a costly affair. Pertusis or

whooping cough is caused by air borne highly contagious bacterium *Bordetella pertussis*. Children are more vulnerable and 95% of global populations are affected and 5 lacs people die each year. Approximately 60 to 80% respiratory diseases are of bacterial origin.

The Enigma of COVID 19 Pandemic And Human Health: Mammals and birds are known to suffer from disease due to Corona virus infection. This Pandemic Covid 19 (nCoV) was renamed SARSCoV (WHO), it belongs to Orthocoronavirinae subfamily, a Riboviria (Singh et al., 2021), is suspected to be transmitted as droplets either directly or indirectly through fomites from person to person (Chan et al., 2020; Faridi et al., 2020). According to a study in China extensive numbers of coronavirus that proliferate in oropharyngeal secretions of patients at an early stage are shed in air after 20 days (Toekk et al., 2020), asymptomatic transmission have also been reported from Singapore (Wei et al., 2020). The mean or median incubation period of this disease ranges from 5 to 6 days (Linton et al., 2020; Jantinen et al., 2019). Dyspnea, hypoxia in 50% of lung infected individuals as well as respiratory failure, shock or multiorgan failure are few symptomatic spectrums of severe and critical disease stages respectively as a result of Corona infection among other several symptoms (Chan et al., 2020; Bajema et al., 2020, Tabata et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020). Mild respiratory disease in human is caused by HKU1, NL63, 229E and OC43 (Nagargoje et al., 2021). In Guangdong province of China in 2002 - 2003, the transmission of beta - Coronavirus occurred from bats to civet cat to human that was described as SARS Coronavirus. Later in 2012, in Saudi Arabia the Middle East RS - CoV was spread from bats to camels to humans. Both types killed many humans (Tanu Singhal, 2019). Covid 19 is caused by newly emerged SARS - Coronavirus-2 (WHO, December 2019) it spread in Wuhan in China and assumed a pandemic proportion globally.

Algal Domain Of Aeromicrobiology:

The density, shape, water vapour, air movements etc., determines the height at which algae are present in the air. Plying of vehicles facilitate far and wide spread as well as increase the "aerobuoyant or aerofloating" duration of single as well as filamentous algal species and their dominance. Moreover, the occurrence of propagules of algae, algae - fungi i.e the lichens, the aeroallergens like hair, fur, feather, etc., of animal origin are influenced by the above factors (D.R.Saxena). Investigation (Ramalingam, 1971) of air at Mysore revealed presence of algae like diatoms, Spirogyra, Oscillatoria, Protococcus, etc. In another aeromicrobiology survey Satya Prakash Saraswati(1974) documented lichen aerosporas of Cladonia, Heteroderma,

Parmelia, Usnea, etc in hilly areas of U.P. In general algae and spores of lichen (Agnihotra et al., 1977) in the air are found at about 2 meters above ground. The walls of Tajmahal are a testimony of growth of aero deposited algae over it. Conservation of heritage is necessary to prevent their degradation (Tilak and Vishwe, 1979).

Aeroallergen Related Respiratory Ailments: The plant biodiversity at any place globally dictates the aeroallergen types disseminated and suspended in the atmosphere. The authors suggest that most settled pollen grains that are very light in weight are again resuspended and further dispersed by wind current. Transport vehicles also contribute in residential and roadways blowing of dust and pollen grains, their distribution and dissemination. The vegetation type generate variety of pollen grains (D.R.Saxena). Asteraceae, Poaceae, Chenopodiaceae, Amaranthaceae are some families that produce aero-pollen-allergens. Investigation by Tilak and Vishwe (1972 and 1975) included 33 pollen types the dominant being the herb type, the water, wind and insects disseminated the aeroallergens far and wide. Seasonal variations due to weather/ climatic conditions is a significant factor in causing respiratory allergies to humans. The potential of different plant pollen allergens in Calcutta city like *Areca catechu*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Carica papaya*, *Phoenix*, *Datura* and *Catharanthus* rely on their chemical characteristics carbohydrates, lipids, and proteins impart chemical variations to pollen types; (Chakroborty et al., 1998); order of clinical aero - pollen - allergen sensitivity indicate *A.indica* 49 %, *Datura* 35 % and *Catharanthus* 26 % potentiality; the variation of all the three pollen constituents ratio wise i.e., carbohydrates, proteins, lipids and their derivatives make them either more allergic (biosilica in grass) or non-allergic to humans and animals also, also presence of external morphological structures like hairs, etc ., impart them allergic properties due to adhesiveness thereby facilitating penetration in lung tissue aggravating endophagocytosis, intracellular lysosomal digestion, macrophage digestion, etc., in lung cells as well as cytokine and chemokine humoral secretions that evoke hypersensitivity (D.R.Saxena hypothesis). Chlamydia are transmitted through air, *C. psitacci* and *C.trachomatis* are etiological agents of severe pneumonia and trachoma of eye diseases in humans. The V.P.Chest Institute at Delhi and centres at Jaipur, Kanpur, Lucknow, Kolkata and Aurangabad (Tilak and Vishwe 1979) examined the allergic patients and isolated respiratory allergic spores of several fungal species like *Rhizopus*, *Cladosporium*, *Curvularia*, *Phoma*, *Helminthosporium*, *Penicillium*, *Nigrospora*, *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus*, *Cephalosporium* etc.

Aflatoxin Producing Airborne Fungi And Diseases:

Severe airborne inoculum of *A. flavus* cause heavy losses to nonirrigated maize crops according to Bilgrami and Choudhary (1999). Similarly, 92 % relative humidity during July-August when temperature is high is an ideal environmental condition for growth of these fungi and abundance of spores and its dissemination in maize fields causing heavy losses (Choudhary,1991).At harvest and storage in different parts of India the humans are exposed to these aflatoxin producing fungi (Bilgrami et al., 1975 - 1996). *A. parasiticus* and the carcinogenic *A.flavus* including other species secrete aflatoxin. The poultry raised in areas containing 70 % or more suspended spores of *A.flavus* have been implicated in spread of lethal poultry disease in Turkey. The toxic strains of the fungi was detected in poultry indoor sheds about 10 to 100 times more than outdoor samples collected by Rati and Ramalingam (1979).The poultry birds exhibited lethal subcutaneous haemorrhages, at autopsy liver appeared pale, fatty, necrotic with biliary proliferation; adrenals, skin, lungs, etc., showed symptoms of damage (Bilgrami and Sinha, 1993).DNA of plants and animals undergo mutagenic breakdown as a result of aflatoxin B1 toxicity. In a study performed by Sinha et al., (1987) on all and individual chromosome of bone marrow cells of mice. He described that the distal parts of chromosomes underwent greater breakages than other regions because of deleterious effect of aflatoxin B1. *Aspergillus fumigatus* grows on tree barks and conidia growth imparts white colour humans acquire spores through spore inhalation leading to pulmonary and bronchopulmonary aspergillosis respectively (Segregatain, 1962; Ikenoto et al., 1972).

Plant Pollen Grains Biochemical Constituents And Allergens In The Atmosphere: The grass pollen grains cause allergic response in 20% population of Americans and Europeans (Gracia and Mozo, 2017), average diameter of *Phleum pratense* PGs lie in the range 30-35 μm ; on lysis the pollen allergens are dispersed as aerosol and nearly 100 variable protein types have been detected as well as classified into 11 groups. The 1a, 1b to 5a, 5b groups are potent Ph1p pollen allergens the pollen cytoplasmic protein granules and other bioactive compounds are also allergic (Pointer et al., 2020; Suphioglu et al., 1992).Moreover the pollen lipids (Gonzalez Roldan et al., 2019), protease, NADPH oxidation as well as particulate pollutants adsorbed on pollen can also evoke immune response in human (Senechal et al., 2015; Visez et al., 2020).the pesticides and insecticides like organochlorines and organophosphorus, etc., in ultra or nano size droplets adsorbed on pollens when inhaled sensitized the human lungs to trigger hypersensitive respiratory and humoral responses (D.R.Saxena).The Ph1p and PCG water insoluble allergens trigger central mediated inflammation, while water soluble allergens

evoke peripheral humoral response respectively (Abou Chakra et al., 2011 b). Immunogold labelling help in locating allergens groups in outer and inner parts of PPPGs.

The surface coats and probably the cytoplasm of pollen grains produces ROS (Boldogh et al., 2005) and in a short spell create oxidation stress thereby causing inflammation in the mouse lung epithelium on being inhaled (Wang et al., 2009). Pollen grains of trees like Betulaceae, Cupressaceae and Taxodiaceae as well as grasses like Loliums, Phleum, etc., as well as weed PGs are allergenic in nature (ANSES, 2014). The PPPG are bioarchitected from molecular compounds like the sporopollenin, oligosaccharides or polysaccharides, some allergic as well as non - allergic proteins, amino acids, lipids and Si and Ca, but protease and NADPH oxidase are absent according to Taylor et al., 2007. Researches have revealed presence of cysteine protease, Ph1p Exy an endoxylanase (Bashir ME et al., 2013; www.allergome.org) and Ph1p Fe/Mn super oxide dismutase (Conti et al., 2014). PCG extract contain Ph1p 11 while Ph1p 1, 2, 4, 6 and 12 occur in PPPG (Abou Chakra et al., 2012). Relative humidity influence expulsion of proteins and other allergens from PPPG (Fritzsche et al., 1997). Alpha - linolenic acid undergo peroxidation to yield phytoprostanoids which is an indicator of oxidative stress in plants and is an ingredient of PPPGs; a combination of glycerol and phytoprostanoids cause degranulation of mast cells (Gillies et al., 2012, Mueller et al.2016). Pollen grains experience an oxidative stress due to PAHs and metals that are part of atmosphere. Such polluted PGs on reaching the human lung epithelium trigger an oxidative stress (Shiraiwa et al., 2012, Smiljanic et al., 2019). Pollen microbiome comprise of DNA of bacteria and fungi adhering on its surface, also microbiome lipid is quantified using ELISA technique and have been suspected in sensitization of human subjects (Bublin et al., 2014). Water soluble E-2 prostaglandin and B-4 like leukotriene present in PPPG function as mediators of allergic response in humans.

Microorganisms Associated Cosmetology:

Microorganisms are omnipresent and cause spoilage, partial and complete degradation of cosmetic products that are externally applied as creams, gels, lipsticks, body sprays, lotions, eyeliner, dyes, perfumes, bindi, etc. As these cosmetics contain carbon compounds it is utilized for chemotropism by microorganism to proliferate. According to the authors of this article certain toxic end products may be generated during decomposition of chemical ingredients incorporated in cosmetic products that have been already applied on human body. Certain mycotoxins and bacteriotoxins are released from the air borne

microorganisms. The end toxic by products and microbial toxins causes allergic reactions on skin, irritation as well as inflammation of eyes, lips, skin, rashes, scars, etc (Sinski,1974) in the body. Microorganisms like *Candida*, *Torula*, *Trichoderma*, *Fusarium*, *Cladosporium*, *Aspergillus*, *Alternaria*, *B.subtilis*, etc., actively cause deterioration of cosmetics. Patch test have been recommended by Pasricha (1988) to ascertain whether the cosmetic products may evoke contact dermatitis reaction or not.

Paraphenylenediamine present in hair dye, shampoos containing selenium sulphide and cetavlon, foaming agents in toothpaste, hair - removers having barium sulphide that exhibit cauterization effect on skin, Para - tertiary - butyl phenol as adhesive on PVC disc used as bindi, mustard oil in hair oils, eosin - dye in lipsticks is a strong photocontact sensitizer, etc., all these chemicals in cosmetic products give positive patch test on human skin initiating contact dermatitis sensitization reaction as well as skin allergies. The symptoms can be noted either immediately or after prolong period. Wounds on skin due to use of cosmetics acquire secondary microbial infections by contact or microbes settling from air, thereby complicating the situation.

Concept Of Phylloplane And Zooplane Microbiology:

Leaf surface is a habitat for microorganisms that settle upon it, the term phyllosphere was individually coined and Ruinen (1956) described it as the ignored milieu of the microorganisms on discovering nitrogen fixing *Beijerinckia* on plant leaves in a survey in Indonesia. Similar observation was made by Last (1955) on wheat and barley leaves harbouring microflora of *sporobolomycetaceae*. Later in 1958, Kerling proposed the term phylloplane for leaf surface and Pugh (1984) explained that rain, splash droplets, gravity aided microflora - sediment deposition, wind impaction, boundary layer transit of microbial propagules by the atmosphere are factors regulating the landing of the spores of microorganisms. The excreta of honey bees, butterflies, other insects provide the necessary nutrients as well as when they chew the leaves the oozing leaf secretions also act as a source of nutrient for proliferation of propagules. Atmospheric temperature, water vapour, UV radiations, etc., affect the phylloplane consortium of microorganisms according to (D.R. Saxena) the bird droppings are also source of nutrition for the propagule growth. Bacteria *Pseudomonas trifoli*, etc., yeasts like *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus diffluens*, *S. cerevisiae*, etc., several fungi species such as *Penicillium oxalicum*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Trichoderma harzianum*, *T. viride*, *Cladosporium cladosporium*, *Drechslera australiensis*, *Aspergillus niger*,

Fusarium oxysporum, *Phoma glomerata*, etc., survive on phylloplane. These may be pathogenic, saprophytic and symbionts, (refer table 3).

Dust Storms Is A Source Of Dissemination of Microorganism: African dust storms carry 25 genus of microorganisms, that were isolated from Caribbean air and can be denoted in % decreasing order of abundance: *Microbacterium* > *Sphingomonas* > *Bacillus* > *Gordonia* > *Staphylococcus*; these occur in marine aerosol spray environment and were identified using 16S rRNA gene sequences (Griffin et al., 2001, Griffin et al., 2003). Nearly 10^8 /gm of virus occur in dust storms, their survival depends on many physicochemical factors (Yates and Yates, 1988), it has been hypothesized that transoceanic dispersal of dust storm borne viruses are possible (Griffin et al., 2001, Griffin et al. 2007). Several substantial evidences point towards the fact that concentrated crustal particles of dust storms spread asthma, allergy, and silicosis pulmonary fibrosis in humans (Chang et al., 2006, Kwon et al., 2002, Norboo et al., 1991, Park et al., 2005, O'Hara et al., 2000, Saiyed et al., 1991, and Xu et al., 1993). Globally one gram of top forest soil incorporates approx. 10^7 while arid and other soil types harbour nearly 10^9 diverse prokaryote communities and their viable propagules.

Approx 10,000 types of bacteria (0.1% of total population) amounting to nearly 99.9% of the diversity (Whitmann et al., 1998, Carmi and Eisenstark 1986, Carlton et al., 2001; Dose et al., 2001; Papova et al., 2002; Gans et al., 2005; Torsvik et al., 1990; UNDP 1997). Out of this 0 to 10^7 gm⁻¹ belong to culturable desert prokaryote (Kwasi et al., 1998; Maeir et al., 2004; Navarro-Gonzalez et al., 2003), the dominant being Protobacteria, Acidobacter and Actinomycetes (Janssen 2006).

According to D.R.Saxena the body surface exoskeleton of invertebrate and vertebrate animals in attached and detached states constitute the "Zooplane" for deposition and dissemination of aero-microbe, aqua-microbe as well as soil-microbe of single species and multispecies assemblages or consortium of microbes. The feathers of aves, hair-fur of mammals (bats) and cuticle of wings-body of insects; scales, fins, barbels of fishes act as substratum for growth of propagules; bacterial as well as fungal cells. The movement of animals in terrestrial, aerial and aquatic habitats help in spread of microbes continentally and also intracontinentally. The body slimy/ watery secretions and excretions all serve as vehicles for landing and deposition of nonpathogenic and pathogenic microorganisms including viruses and prions. The carcasses consumed by guilds of predators - scavengers also disseminate microorganisms that are airborne, contact borne, etc. The interspecies horizontal transfer of genetic material occurs in a

compatible manner, thereby conferring evolutionary, new adaptation and potentials to them to survive and resist hazardous conditions of climate change. These evolved microorganisms continue to cause diseases in their nonspecific and specific hosts and are difficult to be killed or eradicated by novel advanced drugs or vaccines therapies. Thus, total eradication, disease free globally animal and human populations are impossible.

Impact Of Climate Change On Frequency Of Desert Dust Storms Associated

Aeromicrobiology: Globally until 2007 approximately 3.5 - 5.0 billion tons (Perkins, 2001) desert surface soils had disseminated during desert storms from major deserts like the Sahara and Sahal (N.Africa) that amounted to 50 - 75% of share; while the Gobi, Takla Makan and the Badain Jaran deserts of Asia experienced frequent storms. Climate change has converted more areas into desert and frequency of dust storms has increased in Asia in the last 20 years (Goudie and Middleton 2000, Moulin et al., 1997 Zhang et al., 2003, al., Prospero et al., 2005; in China since 1975 to 1987 approximately 2100 km²yr⁻¹ area transformed into desert (Zhenda and Tao,1993). Incidences of dust storms occur in the Great Basin (USA), Sahara de Uyuni (Central and South USA), Etosha and Mkgadikgadi basin (Central Australia, South USA) and the Middle East (Washington et al., 2003). Massive scale soil and dust storms is a continent wide, trans - oceanic global phenomenon (Gillies et al., 1996, Qian et al., 2002) that happens due to high wind velocity due to high temperatures. A duration of 7 - 9 days are required by Asian seasonal (Feb- May) dust storms to cross the Pacific ocean (Xiao et al., 2002), but regular year round dust storms occur that originate from N.Africa affecting native air quality and also in the Middle East, Europe, Asia, the Caribbean including America; the N.Atlantic oscillations and El-Nino, etc., create latitudinal movements of dust storms throughout the year (Goudie and Middleton, 2001, Graham and Duce 1979, Middleton and Goudie, 2001, Moulin et al.,1997,Prospero 1999 and Prospero et al., 2005). According to D.R. Saxena all nuclei of dust particles do not carry pathogenic microorganisms but also bacterial-mycoviral-aeroallergens consortium as well as monospecies aeroallergens are the causes of bronchitis, asthma, cancer, etc., in animals and humans. According to calculations (Blue,1938), an individual inhales on an average 6.6240 gm of dust during dust storms, the particle size smaller than 10 µm may pierce lung epithelium, while those smaller than 2.5 µm may reach subepithelium tissue of lung initiating condition of oxidative stress (Delfino et al., 2005, Donaldson et al., 2001, Zanobetti and Schwartz 2005). About 17 - fold rise in allergy, silicosis and lung fibrosis were reported from Middle East, and the Caribbean (Al Frayh et al., 2001, Benner 1996, Howit 2000, Howit et al.,1988, Prospero 1999).The authors of this review article

agree that allergens, fungal spores, plant and grass pollens, anthropogenic vehicular dust cum emissions and organic detritus impair or affect lung functions (Moore and Norton 1995, Ichinose et al., 2006 and Kwasi 2003).

Classical And Novel Techniques Applied To Identify Desert storm Borne Microorganisms :

The fatty acid methyl esters, 16SrRNA gene sequencing, 18SrRNA gene sequencing, 26SrRNA gene sequencing, microscopy, etc., techniques were used to identify and count bacteria and fungal genera respectively in air borne dust storm samples collected (Griffin, 2007); petridish with nutrient agar, glycerine coated appropriate size metal plates were placed on/in the aircraft to procure microorganisms cultures to estimate species and count the microbial flora

(Griffin 2004, Meier 1936, Meier and Lindbergh 1935, Meier and Artschwager 1938). The desert dust storm air sampler (Andersen 6STG type sampler), air pump devices, portable air pumps have been used, but these methods proved less efficient for collecting virus, as well as recovery of collected bacteria and fungi samples (Stewart et al.,1995). High flow rates of more than 100 litre/ m⁻¹ using centrifugal concentration method appears to be more efficient for sampling desert dust aeromicrobiology (William et al., 2001), but the viability of microorganisms is affected (Wast et al., 2003).

The microscopy provide limited information regarding identification of microorganisms based on staining properties, morphology of cells, pigmentation (that protect against damage and death by UV, extremes of temperatures in deserts, volcanic eruptions in ocean trenches, terrestrial volcanic erupted lava, dust, gases etc.), etc. Antigen - antibody tagged with reporter gene is an immunological method and FISH is another technique that are highly reliable for identification and statistical counts of microorganisms (Chan et al., 2019, Delong et al., 1998, Noble and Furman, 1998, Paul 1982, Thrane et al., 1999, Vessey et al., 1994).The epifluorescence microscopy relies on the nucleic acid staining methods to identify, enlist and count various virus particles suspended and transmitted by desert dust storms and its aerosolized forms; in studies conducted in U.S.Virgin Island and African desert dust storms respectively, 1.8 x 10⁴ m⁻³ and 2.3 X 10⁵m⁻³ viral particles were recorded (Griffin et. al., 2001). Community composition of microorganism strains that are present in very low numbers are detected using high throughput methods like PCR (nucleic acid amplification) as well as nucleic acid sequence based amplification for conserved ribosome genes (Compton 1991,

Mullis et al., 1986, Patterson et al., 2005), after this step employing ecological based gene chips as well as the clone library analysis are performed to identify these microorganisms (Chandler et al., 1997, Walsh and Steidinger 2001).

There are several ingredients in desert dust storms when inhaled by rats and mouse suppress immune system depending on the amount inhaled. Enhanced count of neutrophils, eosinophils, lymphocytes was detected in the blood. The interleukin-2 as well as the alpha tumor necrosis factor also elevated in the above animals (Ichinose et al., 2006, Lei et al., 2004). The alveolar macrophages became non-functional on exposure to constituents of desert dust storms the reason being destruction of nitrogenous bases of DNA and an escalation in the reactive oxygen species (Ezeamuzie et al., 1998, Prahlad et al., 2001).

Indoor Areas And House Dust Mites: House dust mite *Dermatophagoides farinae*, *D.domestica*, *D.destructor*, *D.gallinae*, are allergic to humans. Nearly all residential areas harbour *D.pteronysinus* one of the most widely distributed (90%) and common allergic mite that invade the pillows, blankets, mattresses, used clothes, etc. All the above species derive nourishment from large amount of body skin shed from children, and some skin shed by adults. The domestic servants, housewives, decorators, upholsters, laundry cleaners, hospital laundry cleaners, etc., unconsciously come in direct contact of body parts as well as faeces of the dead dust mites that are equally potent allergens as the live mites (Cunnington, 1972); mite faeces are regarded as the main and major source of house dust allergens in mite culture as revealed by radioimmunoassay studies (Torrey et al., 1981); private and public transport vehicles, used bedsheets in hostels, religious dormitories, wedding ceremony halls, etc., are the most common community source of spread of livehouse dust mite their life cycle stages as well as dead parts of mite allergens (D.R.Saxena). Other potent allergens present in house dust include the small insects, degraded cloth fabric, wool dust of furniture, hairs, wool fibre, bacterial consortium, etc. (authors).

Aeromicrobiology Of Rural, Semiurban And Urban Areas: In residential areas in rural, semiurban as well as cities including metropolitans there are more cases of people suffering either from nonpathogenic respiratory, pathogenic and intermediate of these two respiratory problem. The various permanent anthropogenic factors include plying of two and four wheeler vehicles as a means of routine 24 hour transport mostly in urban and semiurban areas and internal as well as highway routes results in continuous existence of suspended variable size particles, plant and animal allergens and microbes. Bronchitis, asthma and emphysema

ailments are common in all age groups of populations globally and regionally. Occupational associated lung ailments are silicosis, asbestosis, etc., in workers working in coal mine, mineral mines, industrial, construction, agriculture sectors, etc., the atmosphere in these areas are constant sources of microbes, pesticides, chemicals, etc., (from both natural and anthropogenic sources). Anton Von Pirquet (1906) coined the word allergy for foreign substance entering and altering the body immune responses leading to hypersensitivity (refer table 2 for aeroallergens). A new nomenclature have been introduced by WHO International Union of Immunological Society of Allergens: Der P1, Der P2 means the mite allergens, *Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus* is an abbreviated form (first 3 letter from genus and first letter from species and a number). Now italicised names are not used. Out of the 4 major allergic Types, the dominant is Type - I followed by Type - II in vast numbers of communities throughout the world, although their % varies geographically (D.R.Saxena) depending on immunity, nutritional status, GDP/ per capita income, hygiene and cleaner environmental conditions (hygiene and Sanitation Standard Index, criteria proposed - based on GDP by the authors, 2024). Type - I is IgE dependent, Type - II is based on cytotoxic tissue specificity antibody, Type - III is dependent on toxic antigen - antibody complexes with activated complement systems and Type - IV is due to T - lymphocyte cell influenced hypersensitive responses. According to authors of this article, Dharavi (Bombay, India) one of the biggest slum is facing several health problems due to overcrowding, the major being respiratory illnesses that kill infants, children and old populations.

Effect Of Radiation On Indoor And Outdoor Aeromicrobiology :

Based on the property of marine algae to bioconcentrate radionuclides like thorium, uranium and radium a hypothesis have been advanced (D.R.Saxena) that dispersal of such radionuclide storing algae through marine spray (bioradioaerosol) that later persist in air as dry bioradioaerosol, when it is inhaled may cause mutations in lung epithelium, circulatory, integumentary and other systems of humans and mammals leading to malignant lung tumors, leukaemia, teratogenesis (developing foetus in pregnant mothers), etc., in the exposed humans and terrestrial vertebrates. After phagocytosis by respiratory epithelium the lysosomal hydrolytic enzymes are released to destroy the bioradioaerosols. On the contrary direct effect of algal radioaerosol on bacteria, fungi and bacteriophage may kill pathogenic microbes otherwise harmful to humans and animals (microbial-radio-induced-therapy for humans and animals/MRITH). Indirect effect of "algal-radio-aerosol" on pathogenic air borne fungi, bacteria, etc., include loss of pathogenicity after infection due to impairment in the molecular

synthesis and secretion of mycotoxins and bacterial toxins. This is also true for the processed and unprocessed food items that becomes contaminated by airborne radiosensitized pathogenic microbes and that haven't been treated by gamma - radiations to enhance its shelf life. There are experimental evidences in bacteria and fungi regarding lethality of direct effect of radiation. This happens by free hydroxyl radicals produced in cells after radiation exposures that are capable of removing the hydrogen atoms from within the DNA strands, such abnormal DNA structural changes are not self-repairable by mechanisms existing in the microbes (Akhila et al., 2021). However, double or multiple breaks in single strands of DNA make the pathogenic microorganisms make them inactive i.e., non - pathogenic (Munir and Frederighi 2020). Further there are proofs that bacteria, archaea as well as eukaryotes in general can tolerate severe UV radiations, temperature, etc. (Confalonieri and Sommer, 2011). Moreover the ions and free radicals are generated in the matter when radiations pass through them, the hydroxyl radicals cause multiple types of DNA damages; multiple DNA damages similar to oxidative induced damages occurring in endogenous aerobic metabolism have been suggested (Fernandez et al., 2006; Takeshi et al., 2003; Azzam et al., 2012).

In another experimental investigation on the bacterium *Deinococcus radiodurans* (While et al., (1999) discovered that it is radioresistant and its viability as well as ability to express foreign genes is not affected after exposure to a dose of 60 Gy/h radioactive wastes existing at most of the sites (Lange et al., 1998).

Volcanic Eruptions Influence On Aeromicrobiology And Climate Change:

Globally whenever major volcanic eruptions had occurred it had impacted the climate change and vegetation. Alteration takes place in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems in vicinity of the volcanoes (Payne and Egan 2018, Dale et al., 2008; Telford et al., 2004; Zeilinski 2015, Sigl et al., 2015; Robock 2000). Emissions of molten lava called tephra, gaseous clouds and hot solids influence factors like physical and chemical that cause burning of vegetation, until the occurrence of recovery of original vegetation there is partial or total impairment of pollination (Arnalds 2013), thereby reducing suspended pollen grains in the atmosphere. The tephra material along with ammonia, sulphur dioxide, carbon dioxide, sulphuric aerosols persist for prolonged period in the atmosphere (Payne et al., 2019). An elevation in Poaceae pollen can be experienced post Laacher See tephra (LST). Outbreak of volcanic fires, also increase in deposition of Santorini tephra layer in turn enhances the amount of micro - fossils as well as nonsiliceous aquatic pollen (Dale et al., 2008). The pollen dispersal affect aeromicrobiology as

it acts as floating islands for landing and spread of several microbes and their propagule stage (D.R Saxena) that may cause respiratory and other allergic responses to humans and animals.

Solar Aeromicrobiology Model can be employed to reduce microbial counts per cubic centimeter volume of the air under consideration in the environment. Extermination to extinction of nonpathogenic and pathogenic microbes seems to be impossible due to their importance in the life of organisms that exist on earth. The poliovirus ampoules are currently not being destroyed. The high efficiency particulate filter system direct certain volume of air with a uniform velocity to make it free of $0.3\mu\text{m}$ dust particles and microbes also. The authors speculate the use of nanofilters of carbon for this purpose and also to kill microbes due to nanomaterial toxicity.

The proposed aeromicrobiology model can be an installed or portable model that operates using electricity generated from solar panel to incinerate or sterilize the microbes in air samples, there by promoting application of confluence of vedic and science that is actually an East - West Green Technology (EWGT sterilization). This model is a substitute for the ancient vedic Agnihotra practiced twice a day in Indian homes (is a miniature scale hom or yagya involving burning of various medicinal herbs, vegetables, grains , etc) to purify the atmosphere; medicinal smoke of Agnihotra declines the airborne bacteria (Nautiyal et al., 2007). The model envisages control of aeromicroflora without using firewood, the high temperature is achieved by solar heating. It also curbs chemical pollution toxicity that occurs by excessive use of disinfectants in residential, commercial and hospitals respectively. The body compartments and every part of the solar aeromicrobiology model must be fabricated from carbon nanomaterial "fullerene" and other novel nanomaterials. An alternative portable version of this model can have laser beam emitting device self powered by solar energy batteries to sterilize the air samples. Laser beam technology is used to bore a hole in animal cells to deliver DNA. QDS , quantum dots can be used in gene silencing/ siRNA and Tumor targeting, as well as for destroying aeromicroorganism to purify air. Laser will lyse the cells of fungi, bacteria as well as algae that are aeroallergens. Moreover, QDS fabricated from CdS nanoparticles is toxic to cells, organism as observed in vivo experiments as they release ions of cadmium. Apart from this the HPES filter can be manufactured from such toxic nanomaterials i.e., QDS and Carbon nanowire filters having pore size from $0.075\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ to $0.3\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ that may kill the microbes present in air, soil and water. The above miniature models can be installed in air conditioners, cooler-air ducts, slaughter houses, agricultural - food processing industries, pharmaceutical, tissue and stem cell culture laboratories, public and

private toilets as well as bathrooms, etc. Of course the toxic effects of above strategies on humans must be considered as a safety measure, etc.

Conclusion: According to (D.R.Saxena hypothesis, all pathogenic and nonpathogenic aeromicrobes are transmitted through conversion into bioaerosols after gaining entrance into animals and human: air - respiratory cum digestive and excretory system cycle respectively (ARDC i.e., air - respiratory - digestive - air; or ARDEC i.e., air-respiratory-digestive cum excretory - air cycle; both cycles may occur simultaneously or alone). Bioaerosols emanate through nose, mouth, faeces and urine routes. Another route of origin of dry - bioaerosol as well as wet-bioaerosols is the air cum skin-air (hair, fur, feather and scales) cycle (i.e., air-integument-air cycle, AIC or ASC). The bioaerosols return microbe/s to air. The Air-Soil-Water is a conjugated microbial cycle (Environment - Zoonotic - Environment Microbial cycle, EZMC). The water vapour from aquatic ecosystems and the rains are an important link of the proposed cycles in disseminating the propagules and cells of microorganisms (D.R.Saxena).

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*The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Table 1: Phylloplane pathogens and their diseases.

Sr. No.	Pathogen	Disease
	<i>Albugo candida</i>	White rust of crucifers
	<i>Alternaria brassicae</i>	Leaf spot of crucifers
	<i>A solani</i>	Early blight of potato
	<i>Cercospora arachidicola</i> and <i>C. personata</i>	Leaf spot or tikka disease of groundnut
	<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	Leaf and fruit disease
	<i>Erysiphe graminis tritici</i>	Powdery mildew of wheat
	<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i>	Brown spot of paddy
	<i>Melampsora lini</i>	Rust of linseed
	<i>Peronospora parasitica</i>	Downy mildew of crucifers
	<i>P. viciae</i>	Downy mildew of pea, beans
	<i>Plasmopara viticola</i>	Downy mildew of grape-vine
	<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i>	Rice blast disease
	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>	Late blight of potato
	<i>Puccinia graminis tritici</i>	Rust disease of wheat
	<i>Taphrina deformans</i>	Peach leaf curl
	<i>T. maculans</i>	Leaf spot of turmeric and zinger
	<i>Uromyces fabae</i>	Rust of pea

Table 2: Aeroallergens commonly encountered in nature.

Sr. No.	Aeroallergens	Examples
	Algae	Aulosira, Chlamydomonas, Lyngbya, Nostoc, Phormidium, Gloeotrichia, diatoms, Oscillatoria, Chlorella, Plectonema,
	Fungi	Alternaria, Aspergillus, Candida, Chaetomium, Curvularia, Fusarium, Monilia, Penicillium, Phoma, Trichoderma
	Lichens	Cladonia, Heterodermia, Parmelia, Usnea
	Pollen grains	Ageratum conyzoides, Amaranthus sp., Argemone mexicana, Azadirachta indica, Carica papaya, Cassia fistula, Cocos nucifera, Croton, Datura metel, Catharanthus roseus, Euphorbia hirta, Ocimum sanctum, Parthenium hysterophorus, Ricinus communis, Setaria sp., Phoenix sylvestris.
	Others	Dust, mites, viruses, bacteria, protozoa, moss spores, fern spores, seed spiders, etc.

Table 3: Some common aeroallergens (Source: Finkelstein, 1969)

Sr. No.	Aeroallergens	Sources
	Pollen grains	Wind-pollinated plants e.g. grasses, weeds, trees
	Moulds	Saprophytic fungi multiply on dead organic substrate in the presence of optimum moisture and temperature
	Danders	Feathers of chickens, ducks, hairs of cat, dogs, sheep, cattle, laboratory animals and humans.
	House dust	A composite of all dust containing specific components related to mites, algae, etc.
	Cosmetics	Talcs, perfume, hair tonics, lotions, bindi, etc.
	Insecticides	Insecticides containing pyrethrum as a common ingredient.
	Paint and varnishes	Linseed oil, organic solvents act as irritant. darbox

Table 4: Use of dilution plate technique to study the distribution of fungi ($\text{cm}^{-3} \times 10^3$) on floral parts of guava (Pandey, 1990)

Sr. No.	Fungal species	Unopened bud	Floral parts Petals	Sepals
	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	28	6	9
	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	--	1	--
	<i>A. niger</i>	3	2	
	<i>Aureobasidium pullulans</i>	32	8	19
	<i>Candida sp.</i>	1	--	--
	<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>	37	14	17
	<i>C. herbarum</i>	4	2	--
	<i>Drechslera australiensis</i>	2	--	5
	<i>Epicoccum purpurascens</i>	10	2	12
	<i>F. semetectum</i>	3	3	24
	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	7	--	5
	<i>Pestalotia psidii</i>	--	--	4
	White sterile mycelia	--	--	1
	Yellow sterile mycelia	--	--	2

References

- Abdel-Hafez, S. I. I. 1982. Cellulose-decomposing fungi of desert soils in Saudi Arabia. *Mycopathologia* 78:73–78.
- Abdel-Hafez, S. I. I. 1982. Survey of the mycoflora of desert soils in Saudi Arabia. *Mycopathologia* 80:3–8.
- Abdel-Hafez, S. I. I., A. A. M. Shoreit, A. I. I. Abdel-Hafez, and M. O. E. Maghraby. 1986. Mycoflora and mycotoxin-producing fungi of air-dust particles from Egypt. *Mycopathologia* 93:25–32.

Abdel-Hafez, S. I. I., and A. A. M. Shoreit. 1985. Mycotoxins producing fungi and mycoflora of air-dust from Taif, Saudi Arabia. *Mycopathologia* 92:65–71.

AbouChakra,O.,Rogerieux,F.,Poncet,P.,Sutra,J.-P.,Peltre,G.,Sénéchal,H.,Lacroix,G., 2011a.AbilityofPollenCytoplasmicGranulestoInduceBiasedAllergicResponsesina Rat Model. *Int. Arch. Allergy Immunol.*154,128–136.<https://doi.org/10.1159/000320227>.

AbouChakra,O.,Sutra,J.-P.,DemeyThomas,E.,Vinh,J.,Lacroix,G.,Poncet,P.,Sénéchal,H., 2012.ProteomicAnalysisofMajorandMinorAllergensfromIsolatedPollen CytoplasmicGranules.*J.ProteomeRes.*11,1208–1216.

AbouChakra,O.,Sutra,J.-P.,Poncet,P.,Lacroix,G.,Sénéchal,H.,2011b.KeyRoleofWater InsolubleAllergenofPollenCytoplasmicGranulesinBiasedAllergicResponseinaRat. Model. *World Allergy Organ. J.*4, 4–12.563 <https://doi.org/10.1097/WOX.0b013e318205ab44>.

Akhila, P.P. et al., Application of electromagnetic radiation for decontamination of fungi and mycotoxins in food products: A comprehensive review. *Trends in Food Sci and Technol.* 114. 339 - 409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2021.06.013>

Al Frayh, A. R. et al., (2001): Increased prevalence of asthma in Saudi Arabia. *Ann. Allergy. Asthma Immunol.* 86. 292 - 296.

Alford, R.H.(1966): Human Influenza resulting from aerosol inhalation. *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.* 122: 800 - 804.

ANSES,2014.Etatdesconnaissancesurl'impactsanitaireliéàl'expositiondelapopulationgénéraleauxpollens présentsdansl'airambiant.

Archer, G. L. (1998): *Staphylococcus aureus*: a well - armed pathogen. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* 26.1179 - 1181.

Arnalds, O.(2013): The influence of volcanic tephra (ash) on ecosystems.in *Advances in Agronomy* (Ed.Sparks, D.L.) volcanic 121, 331 - 380.

Azevedo, N.F. et al., (2004): Nutrient shock and incubation atmosphere influence recovery of culturable *Helicobacter pylori* from water. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 70. 490 - 493.

Azzam, El. et al., Ionizing radiation - induced metabolic oxidative stress and prolonged cell injury. *Cancer Letters.* 2012; 327: 1 - 2.: 48 - 60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.canlet.2011.12.012>

bacteriophages and bacterial cells. *Ann. Review of Microbiol.* 1967.21: 325 - 368. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.micr.21.1.00167.005145>

Bajema KL, Oster AM, McGovern OL, et al. Persons evaluated for 2019 novel coronavirus United States, January. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep* 2020; 69:166.

Bashir, M.E.H., Lui, J.H., Palmivelu, R., Naclerio, R.M., Preuss, D., 2013a. Pollen Lipidomics: Lipid Profiling Exposes a Notable Diversity in 22 Allergenic Pollen and Potential Biomarkers of the Allergic Immune Response. *PloS One* 8, e57566.

Bashir, M.E.H., Ward, J.M., Cummings, M., Karrar, E.E., Root, M., Mohamed, A.B.A., Naclerio, R.M., Preuss, D., 2013b. Dual Function of Novel Pollen Coat (Surface) Proteins: IgE-binding Capacity and Proteolytic Activity Disrupting the Airway Epithelial Barrier. *PloS One* 8, e53337.

Bener, A. et al., (1996): Genetic and environmental associated with asthma. *Hum. Biol.* 68. 405 - 414.

Bhaduri, R. 1998. Cosmetic allergy; A review. In. *Environmental and Aerobiology* (ed. A.K. Jain) pp. 245-256. Research Periodicals & Book Publ. House, Texas, U.S.A.

Bilgrami, K.S. and Choudhary, A.K. 1990. *Indian Phytopath.* 43: 38-42.

Bilgrami, K.S. and Sinha, K.K. 1993. Mycotoxins - Chemical, biological and environmental aspects. In *Fungal Ecology and Biotechnology* (eds. B. Rai, D. K. Arora, N.K. Dubey and P.D. Sharma). pp. 295-310, Rastogi Publ. Meerut.

Blue, J.A. (1938): Dust - its effect on men from medical standpoint with special reference to the dust bowl. *Southern. Med. J.* 31. 1101 - 1106.

Boldogh, I., Bacsı, A., Choudhury, B.K., Dharajiyā, N., Alam, R., Hazra, T.K., Mitra, S., Goldblum, R.M., Sur, S., 2005. Ros Generated by Pollen NADPH Oxidase Provide a Signal That Augments Antigen-Induced Allergic Airway Inflammation. *J. Clin. Invest.* 115, 2169.

Caimi, P. and A. Eisenstark. (1986): Sensitivity of *Deinococcus radiodurans* to near UV radiations. *Mutat. Res.* 162. 145 - 151.

Carlton, C.A. et al., (2001): Importance of a Martian hematite site for astrobiology. *Astrobiology* 1. 111 - 123.

Chakraborty, P. et al., 1998. Clinical tests and chemical analysis of some common aeroallergens from Calcutta. In *Environmental and Aerobiology* (eds. A.K. Jain). pp. 239-294. Research Periodicals & Book Publ. House, Texas, U.S.A.

Chan JF, Yuan S, Kok KH, et al. A familial cluster of pneumonia associated with the 2019 novel coronavirus indicating person-to-person transmission: A study of a family cluster. *The Lancet* 2020; 395:514-23.

Chandler, D. P. et al., (1997): Effect of PCR template concentration on the composition and distribution of total community 16s DNA clone libraries. *Mol. Ecol.* 6. 475 - 482.

Chang et al., (2006): Correlation of desert dust storm events with daily clinic visit for allergic rhinitis in Tapei, Taiwan. *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health A* 69: 229 - 235.

Chen, F. et al., (2001): Application of digital image analysis and flow cytometry to enumerate marine viruses stained with SYBR gold. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 67. 539 - 545.

Choudhary, A.K. 1991. Ph.D. Thesis. Bhagalpur Univ. Bhagalpur (Bihar). Cunningham, D.D. 1873. Microscopic examination of air. Govt. Printer, Calcutta.

Close, D.M. et al., DNA damage by the direct effect of ionizing radiation: Products Production by two sequential one electron oxidation. *Journal of Physiol Chem A.* 2013; 117(47): 12608 - 12615. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp4084844>

Compton, J. (1991): Nucleic acid sequence - based amplification. *Nature* 350. 91 - 92.

Confalonieri, F. and Sommer, S: Bacteria and archaeal resistance to ionizing radiation. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series.* 2011; 261. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/261/1/012005>

Cook, A.G. et al., (2005): Health effects of natural dust - role of trace elements and compounds. *Biol. Trace Element Res.* 103. 1 - 15.

Cox, M.M and Battista, J.R. 2005: *Deinococcus radiodurans* - The consummate survivor. *Nature Reviews/Microbiology.* 3. pp.882 - 992.

Cunnington, A.M. 1972. House dust mites and respiratory allergy. A qualitative survey of species As occurring in finish house dust. *J. Resp. Dis* 53: 338. 14: 879 - 887.

Dale, V.H., et al., (2008): Effects of volcanic modern eruptions on vegetation. in *Volcanoes and the Environment* (Cambridge Univ Press).

Delfino et al., (2005): Potential role of ultrafine particles in associations between airborne particle mass and cardiovascular health. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 113: 934 - 946.

DeLong, E.F. et al., (1999): Visualization and enumeration of marine planktonic

- archaea and bacteria by using polyribonucleotide probes and fluorescent in situ hybridization. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 65. 5554 - 5563.
- Dewhirst. 2002. Prevalent bacterial species and novel phylotypes in advanced noma lesions. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 40:2187–2191.
- Diels et al., 1995. The CZC operon of *Alcaligenes eutrophus* CH34: from resistance mechanism to the removal of heavy metals. *J. Ind. Microbiology.* 14, pp.142 - 153.
- Donaldson, K. et al., (2001): Ambience particle inhalation and the cardiovascular system: potential mechanisms. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 109. 523 - 527.
- Dose, K. et al., (2001): Survival of microorganisms under the extreme conditions of the Atacama desert. *Orig. Life Evol. Biosph.* 31. 287 - 303.
- Ezeamuzie, C, et al., (1998): Responses of alveolar macrophages to post - Gulf war air borne dust from Kuwait. *Environ. Int.* 24: 213 - 220.
- Faridi S, Niazi S, Sadeghi K. A field indoor air measurement of SARS-CoV-2 in the patient rooms of the largest hospital in Iran. *Sci Total Environ* 2020; 725:138401–138401
- Fritzsche, C., Becker, W.-M., Behrendt, H., 1997. A Method for Investigating the Effects of Gaseous Pollutants on Pollen Ultrastructure and Allergen Release, in: Ring, J., Behrendt, Heidrun, Vieluf, D. (Eds.), *New Trends in Allergy IV*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp.101–103.
- Gans et al., (2005): Computational improvements reveal great bacterial diversity high metal toxicity in soil. *Science.* 309, 1387 -1390.
- Garcia - Mozo, H., 2017: Poaceae pollen as the leading aeroallergen worldwide: A Review. *Allergy* 72, 1849 - 1858. <https://doi.org/10.1111/all.13210>
- Gilles, S., Fekete, A., Zhang, X., Beck, I., Blume, C., Ring, J., Schmidt-Weber, C., Behrendt, H., Schmitt-Kopplin, P., Traidl-Hoffmann, C., 2011. Pollen Metabolome Analysis Reveals Adenosine as a Major Regulator of Dendritic Cell-Primed TH Cell Responses. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.* 127, 454-461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2010.12.1082>.
- Gillies et al., (1996): Dust concentrations of an intense dust haze event: Inland delta region, Mali, W. Africa. *Atmos. Environ.* 30: 1081 - 1090.
- Ginoza, W. et al., The effects of ionizing radiation on nucleic acids of González Roldán, N., Engel, R., Düpow, S., Jakob, K., Koops, F., Orinska, Z., Vigor,

- C., Oger,C.,Galano,J.-M.,Durand,T.,Jappe,U.,Duda,K.A.,2019.LipidMediatorsFrom Timothy Grass Pollen Contribute to the Effector Phase of Allergy and Prime Dendritic CellsforGlycolipidPresentation.Front.Immunol.10.<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2019.00974>.
- Goudie, A.S., and N.J. Middleton. (2001): Sahara desert storms: nature and consequences. *Earth Sci. Rev.* 56: 179 – 204
- Graham W.F. and R.A.Duce (1979): Atmospheric pathways of the phosphorus cycle. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta.*43, 1195 -1208.
- Griffin D.W. (2001): Dust in the wind: long range transport of dust in the atmosphere and its implications for global public and ecosystem health. *Global Change Hum. Health.* 2, 20 - 35.
- Griffin, D.W. (2004): Terrestrial microorganisms at an altitude of 20,000 m in earth's atmosphere. *Aeromicrobiologia* 20: 135 - 140.
- Griffin, D.W. et al., (2007): Airborne dust and aeromicrobiology over Turkish Mediterranean coastline. *Atmosph. Environ.* 41: 4050 - 4062.
- Gupta, G.P. and Singh, K. 1996. Studies on Vedic technology for environmental health. Natl Seminar on Biotech: New Trends and Prospects, Gurukul Kangri Univ., Hardwar, Abstract, pp. 41-42.
- Gupta, G.P. and Singh, K. 1996. Studies on Vedic technology for environmental health.Natl Seminar on Biotech: New Trends and Prospects, GurukulKangri Univ., Hardwar, Abstract, pp. 41-42.
- Harrison, R.M. and J.X.Yin. (2000): Particulate matter in the atmosphere: which particle properties are important for its effects on health? *Sci.Total Environ.* 249. 85 - 101.
- Hassan et al., 2003: Engineering *Deinococcus geothermalis* - for bioremediation of high temperature radioactive waste environments. *Appl. Environ.Microbiol.*69.pp. 4575 - 4582.
- Howit, M.E. (2000): Asthma management in the Caribbean - an update.
- Howit, M.E. et al, (1998): The prevalence of childhood asthma and allergy in Barbados.The Barbados Asthma and Allergy Study. *Am. J. Respir Crit Care Med.*157, A 64.
- Ichinose, T.K. et al., (2005): Enhancement of mite allergen - induced eosinophil

- infiltration in the murine airway and local cytokine/chemokine expression by Asian sand dust. *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health A* 69. 1571 - 1585.
- Ikenoto, H., et al., (1971): Pulmonary aspergillosis. *Sabouraudia*. 9. 30.
- Isemberlinova, A.A. et al., The pulsed X- ray treatment of wheat against pathogenic fungi. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Phys Res Sect. B. Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*. 2012; 503: 75 - 78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2021.07.011>
- Jacobs, W.C. 1991. *American Meteorol. Soc. Boston*. 1103-1111.
- Jain, A.K. 1998. *Environmental and Aerobiology. Research periodicals & Book Publ. House, Texas*.
- Janssen, P.H. (2006): Identifying the soil bacteria taxa in libraries of 16S rRNA and 16S rRNA genes. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 72, 1719 - 1728.
- Joshi, L.M., Sastri, S.E. and Gera, I.D. 1972. Epidemiological aspects of *Puccinia graminis tritici* in India. *Proc. Indian Natl. Sci. Acad.* 37B: 445-453.
- Jung, S. et al., (2018): Grass pollen production and group V allergen content of agriculturally relevant species and cultivars. *PLO ONE* 13, e0193958. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.193958>.
- Kerling, L.C.P. 1958. *Tydschr.Pl. Ziekten*. 64: 402-410.
- Knoke, J. D., T. C. Smith, G. C. Gray, K. S. Kaiser, and A. W. Hawksworth. 2000. Factor analysis of self-reported symptoms: does it identify a Gulf War syndrome? *Am. J. Epidemiol.* 152:379–388.
- Korenyi-Both, A. L., A. L. Korenyi-Both, and D. J. Juncer. 1997. Al Eskan disease: Persian Gulf syndrome. *Military Med.* 62:1–13.
- Kwasi, A.A. (2003): Date palm and sandstorm borne - allergens. *Clin. Exp. Allergy*. 33. 419 - 426.
- Kwasi, A.A. et al, (1998): Aeroallergens and viable microbes in sandstorm dust. Potential triggers of allergic and non - allergic respiratory ailments. *Allergy*. 53. 255 - 265.
- Kwon et al., (2002): Effects of the Asian dust events on daily mortality in Seoul, Korea. *Environ. Res. A* 90 - 91.

La Scola, B., R. J. Birtles, M. N. Mallet, and D. Raoult. 1998. *Massilia timonae* gen. nov., sp. nov., isolated from blood of an immunocompromised patient with cerebellar lesions. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 36:2847–2852.

Laden, F., L. M. Neas, D. W. Dockery, and J. Schwarz. 2000. Association of fine particulate matter from different sources with daily mortality in six U.S. cities. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 108:941–947.

Lange, et al., 1998: Engineering a recombinant *D. radiodurans* for organopollutant degradation in radioactive mixed waste environment. *Nat. Biotechnol.* 16:pp.929 - 933.

Last, F.T. 1955. *Trans. Br. mycol. Soc.* 38: 221-239.

Lee, H. A., R. Gabriel, J. P. G. Bolton, A. J. Bale, and M. Jackson. 2002. Health status and clinical diagnoses of 3000 UK Gulf War veterans. *J. R. Soc. Med.* 95:491–497.

Lee, H. B., and N. Magan. 1999. Environmental factors and nutritional utilization patterns affect niche overlap indices between *Aspergillus ochraceus* and spoilage fungi. *Lett. Appl. Microbiol.* 28:300–304.

Lee, Y. A., H. J. Kim, T. W. Lee, M. J. Kim, M. H. Lee, J. H. Lee, and C. G. Ihm. 2004. First report of *Cryptococcus albidus*-induced disseminated cryptococcosis in a renal transplant recipient. *Korean J. Intern. Med.* 19:53–57.

Lei, Y. C., C. C. Chan, P. Y. Wang, C. T. Lee, and T. J. Cheng. 2004. Effects of Asian dust event particles on inflammation markers in peripheral blood and bronchoalveolar lavage in pulmonary hypertensive rats. *Environ. Res.* 95:71–76.

Lenes, J. M., B. P. Darrow, C. Cattrall, C. A. Heil, M. Callahan, G. A. Vargo, R. H. Byrne, J. M. Prospero, D. E. Bates, K. A. Fanning, and J. J. Walsh. 2001. Iron fertilization and the *Trichodesmium* response on the West Florida shelf. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 46:1261–1277.

Linton N M, Kobayashi T, Yang Y. Incubation period and other epidemiological characteristics of 2019 novel coronavirus infections with right truncation: A statistical analysis of publicly available case data. *J Clin Med* 2020; 9:E538– E538.

Llyod, J.R. and Lovley, D. 2001: Microbial detoxification of metal and radionuclides. *Curr.opin. Biotechnol.* 22:pp. 248 - 253.

Maidan, A.G. and Reginer, F.E. Proteomic identification of carbonylated proteins and

- their oxidation sites. *Journal of Proteome Research*. 2010; 9(8): 3766 - 3780.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/pr1002609>
- Maier, R.M, et al, (2004): Microbial life in the Atacama desert. *Science*. 306, 1289 - 1290.
- Maisanneuve, E. et al., Rules governing selective protein carbonylation. *PLoS One*. 2009; 4 (10).<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0007269>
- Meier F.C. (1936): Effects of conditions in the stratosphere on spores of fungi. *Natl. Geogr. Stratosph. Ser. 2*, 152 - 153.
- Meier F.C. and C.A. Lindbergh (1935): Collecting microorganisms from Arctic atmospheric. *Science. Monthly*. 40, 5 - 20.
- Meier F.C. and E. Artschwager. (1935): Airplane collection of sugar beet pollen. *Science*. 88, 507 - 508.
- Meng et al., (2020): Coronavirus disease (COVID-19): A Scoping Review. *Euro Surveill*. 25 (15): pii = 2000125. <https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917>
- Middleton, N.J. and A.S. Goudie (2001): Sahara dust: sources and transport. *Inst. Br. Geogr.* 26, 165 - 181.
- Moore, C and R. Norton (2005): *Cornybacterium aquaticum* septicaemia in a neutropenic patient. *J. Clin. Pathol.* 48, 971 - 972.
- Moulin et al., (1997): Control of atmospheric export of dust from N. Africa by the N. Atlantic oscillation. *Nature* 387, 691 - 694.
- Mueller et al., (2016): A metabolomic, geographic, and seasonal analysis of the contribution of pollen - derived adenosine to allergic sensitization. *Metabolomics* 12, 187.
- Mullis, K.F. et al., (1986): Specific enzymatic amplification of DNA in vitro: the polymerase chain reaction. *Cold Harbor Symposium. Quant. Biol.* 1. 263 - 273.
- Munir M.T. and Federighi, M. Control of food borne biological hazards by ionizing radiation. *Foods* 2020; 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9070878>.
- Nagargoje B, Palod A, Dixi J, et al. Seroprevalence of COVID-19 in a city in India: A community Fathima Hinaz Z, et al based cross-sectional study. *J Res Med Dent Sci* 2021; 9:48-53
- Nagarjan, S and Singh, H. 1973. Satellite television cloud photography as a possible tool to forecast plant disease spread. *Curr. Sci.* 42: 273-274.

- Nautiyal, C.S., P.S. Chauhan and Y.L. Nene. 2007. Medicinal smoke reduces airborne bacteria. *J. Ethnopharma.* 114: 446-451.
- Navarro- Gonzalez et al., (2003): Mars like soils in the Atacama desert, Chile, and the dry limit of microbial life. *Science* 302: 1018 - 1021.
- Navneet 1995-96. Aeromycoflora over potato fields. *J. Natural and Physical Sci.* 9-10. 61-71.
- Navneet, Chand, S. and Sharma, V.K. 1998. Agnihotra- the air purifier. Aryabhata (Gurukul Kangri Univ. Hardwar).
- Noble, R. T., and J. A. Furman. 1998. Use of SYBR green I for rapid epifluorescence counts of marine viruses and bacteria. *Aquat. Microbiol. Ecol.* 14:113–118.
- Norboo, T., P. T. Angchuk, M. Yahya, S. R. Kamat, F. D. Pooley, B. Corrin, I. H. Kerr, N. Bruce, and K. P. Ball. 1991. Silicosis in a Himalayan village population: role of environmental dust. *Thorax* 46:861–863. 14: 879 - 887.
- O'Hara, S. L., G. F. S. Wiggs, B. Mamedov, G. Davidson, and R. B. Hubbard. 2000. Exposure to airborne dust contaminated with pesticide in the Aral Sea region. *Lancet* 355:627.
- Ozawa, Y., B. L. Ong, and S. H. An. 2001. Traceback systems used during recent epizootics in Asia. *Rev. Sci. Technique Off. Int. Epizoot.* 20:605–613.
- Pandey, R.R. 1990. Mycoflora associated with flora parts of guava (*Psidium guajava* L). *Acta Botanica Indica.* 18: 59-63.
- Pandey, R.R. Arora, D.K. and Dubey, R.C. 1993. Antagonistic interactions between fungal pathogens and phylloplane fungi of guava. *Mycopath.* 124: 31-39.
- Papastefanou, C., M. Manolopoulou, S. Stoulos, A. Ioannidou, and E. Gerasopoulos. 2001. Coloured rain dust from Sahara Desert is still radioactive. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 55:109–112.
- Papova, N. A., I. A. Nikolaev, T. P. Turova, A. M. Lysenko, G. A. Osipov, N. V. Verkhovtseva, and N. S. Panikov. 2002. *Geobacillus uralicus*, a new species of thermophilic bacteria. *Mikrobiologiya* 71:391–398.
- Park, B. J., K. Sigel, V. Vaz, K. Komatsu, C. McRill, M. Phelan, T. Colman, A. C. Comrie, D. W. Warnock, J. N. Galgiani, and R. A. Hajjeh. 2005. An epidemic of coccidioidomycosis in Arizona associated with climatic changes, 1998–2001. *J. Infect. Dis.* 191:1981–1987.

Park, D. J., J. C. Yun, J. E. Baek, E. Y. Jung, D. W. Lee, M. A. Kim, and S. H. Chang. 2006. Relapsing *Bacillus licheniformis* peritonitis in a continuous ambulatory peritoneal dialysis patient. *Nephrology* 11:21–22.

Paul, J.H.(1982): Use of Hoechst dyes 33258 and 3342 for enumeration of attached and planktonic bacteria. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 43, 939 - 994.

Payne, R.J.and Egan, J.(2019): Using palaeontological technique to understand the impacts of past volcanic eruptions. *Quat. Intl.* 499, 278 – 289

Perkins, S.(2001): Dust the thermostat. *Science. News* 160, 200 - 201.

Picarski et al., (2023): Volcanic impact on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems in the Eastern Mediterranean 4.167/ *Communications Earth & Environment*/<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-00827-0>.www.nature.com/commsenv, pp 1 - 12. Postgrad. Doctor. Caribb.16, 86 - 104.

Prahlad A.K, et al., (2001): Air pollution particle mediated oxidative DNA base damage in cell free system and in airway epithelial cells in relation to particulate metal content and biodiversity. *Chem.Res. Toxicol.*14: 879 - 887. 14: 879 - 887.

Prospero et al., (2005): Inter - hemispheric transport of viable fungi and bacteria from Africa to the Caribbean with soil dust. *Aerobiologia.* 21. 1 – 19

Prospero J.M. (1999): Long - range transport of mineral dust in the global atmosphere: impact of African dust on the environment of the southeastern U.S. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.USA* 96. 3396 - 3403.

Qian et al., (2002): Variation of the dust storm in China and its climatic control.*J. Climate* 15: 1216 - 1229.

Quagliarieli, O.V. and Scheld, W.(1992): Bacterial meningitis: pathogenesis, physiology and progress. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 327 (12): 864 - 871. Bloom, B.(1994): Tuberculosis: pathogenesis, protection and control: *AK.Soc. Microbiol.*

Rai, B. and Singh D.B. 1980. Antagonistic activity of some leaf surface microfungi against *Alternaria brassicae* and *Drechslera graminea*. *Trans Br. mycol. Soc.* 75: 363-369.

Rati, E.A. and Ramalingam, A. 1979. Toxic strains among air-borne isolates of *Aspergillus flavus* Link. *Indian J. Exp. Biol.* 17: 97-98.

Rich, T. et al., Defying death after DNA damage. *Nature.* 2000; 407: 777 -

783.<https://doi.org/10.1038/3507717>

Robock, A.(2000): Volcanic eruptions and climate.Rev.Geophys. 38, 191 -291.

Roshan Lal and Maheshwari, D.K. 1996. Studies on the potential of microflora associated with dhataki flowers (*Woodfordia fruticosa* Kurz.) in the production of Amritarishta. Natl. Seminar on Biotechnology: New Trends & prospects, Gurukul Kangri Univ. Hardwar, Abstr. p. 30-31.

Ruinen, J. 1956. Nature (London). 177: 220-221.

Saiyed et al., (1991): Non - pathogenic Pnuemoconiosis at high altitude villages on central Ladakh. Br. J. Ind. Med. 48: 825 - 829.

Satya Prakash Saraswati 1974. Agnihotra a study from chemical stand point. Jan Gyan Prakashan, New Delhi, p. 106.

Schweizer et al., (2008): Solution structure of Ph1 p 3, a major allergen from Timothy grass pollen. Biol.Chem. 389, 919 - 923. <https://doi.org/10.1514/BC.2008.102>

Segretain, G. (1962): Pulmonary aspergillosis. Lab Investigation. 11: 1046 -1052.

Senechal et al., (2015): A Review of the effects of major atmospheric pollutants on pollen grains, pollen content and allergenicity. Sci. World J., ID 940243.

Sghaier, H. et al., Basal DNA machinery is subject to positive selection in ionizing radiation- resistant bacteria.BMC Genomics. <https://doi.org/10.1186/114/2164 - 1297>

Sharma, V.K. and Navneet. 1996. Aeromycoflora of Gurukul Kangri Pharmacy, Haridwar. National Seminar on Biotechnology: New Trends & Prospects, Gurukul Kangri Univ., Hardwar. Abstr. b. 54. Tilak, S.T. Aerobiology. Vaijayant Prakashan, Aurangabad, p. 207.

Shirawa et al., (2012): Hazardous components and health effects of atmospheric aerosol particles: Reactive oxygen species, Soot, Polycyclic Aromatic Componds and Allergenic Proteins. Free Radic. Res. 46, 927 - 939.

Sigl, M.L. etal., (2015): Timing and climate forcing volcanic eruptions for the past 25000 yrs. Nature 523, 543 - 549.

Singh DK, Garg A, Bagri S, et al. COVID-19 presentation and effect of associated comorbidities on severity of illness at a dedicated COVID hospital in North India. J Res Med Dent Sci 2021; 9:49-54.

Sinking, J.T. (1974): Dermatophytes in human, skin, hair and nails. Springfield, Charles, C. Thomas.

Smiljanic et al., (2019): In - depth quantitative profiling of post transitional

- modifications of Timothy grass pollen allergome in relation to environmental oxidative stress. *Environ. Int.* 126, 644 - 658.
- Stewart, S. et al., (1995): Effect of impact stress on microbial recovery on an agar surface. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 61, 1232 - 1239.
- Suphioglu et al., (1992): Mechanism of grass - pollen - induced asthma. *The Lancet* 339, 569 – 572.
- T Marjatta Rahkio and Hannu J. Korkeala (1997): *J.Food.Protection*, Vol 60, No 1, pp 3842.
- AbouChakra, O., 2009. Allergénicité des granules cytoplasmiques de pollen. Université Paris Diderot, Paris.
- Tabata S, Imai K, Kawano S, et al. Clinical characteristics of COVID-19 in 104 people with SARS-CoV-2 infection on the Diamond Princess cruise ship: A retrospective analysis. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2020; 20:1043.
- Tanaka, M. et al., 2004: *Deinococcus radiodurans* transcriptional response to ionizing radiation desiccation reveals novel proteins that contribute to extreme radio - resistance. *Genetics*. 168, pp 21-33.
- Tanu Singhal. A review of coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19). *Indian J Pediatr* 2020; 87:281–286.
- Tastassa et al., (2024): Aeromicrobiology: A global review of the cycling and relationships of the bioaerosols with the atmosphere. Vol 912, 168478, *Science of Total Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023>.
- Taylor et al., (2002): Release of allergens as aerosols: a link between grass pollen and asthma. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.* 109, 51 - 56.
- Telford, R. et al., (2004): Lacustrine deposit of tephra depositions example from Mexico. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 23, 2337 - 2353.
- Thrane, C. et al., (1999): Vital fluorescent staining for detection of stress in *Pythium ultimum* and *Rhizoctonia solani*. *FEMS Microbiol. Evolution.* 30, 11 - 13.
- Tilak, S.T. and Kulkarni, R.L. 1972. Microbial content of air inside and outside of caves at Aurangabad. *Curr. Sci* -23: 850-851.
- Tilak, S.T. and Vishwe, D.B. 1975. Microbial content of air inside library. *Biovigyanam* 1: 187-190.

Tilak, S.T. and Vishwe, D.B. 1979. Aeropalynology at Aurangabad. IV th Int. Polynological Conf., Lucknow.

Tilak, S.T. et al., 1972. Studies in the microbiological deterioration of paintings at Ajanta and Ellora. *Studies Museumology*. 8: 20-25.

To KKW, Tsang OTY, Leung WS. Temporal profiles of viral load in posterior oropharyngeal saliva samples and serum antibody responses during infection by SARS-CoV-2: An observational cohort study. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2020; S1473-30992030196–1.

Torey, E.R. et al. 1981. Mite faeces are a major source of dust allergens. *Nature*. 289: 592.

Tsorvik, V. et al., (1990): High diversity in DNA of soil bacteria. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 56, 782 - 787.

Tsorvik, V. et al., (2002): Prokaryote diversity - magnitude, dynamics and controlling factors. *Science*. 296, 1064 - 1066.

Upadhyay, R.K and Arora, D.K. 1995-96. Sporostatic nature of neem smoke and its possible ecological influence on air fungal flora of polluted site. *J. Sci. Res. (B.H.U.)* 26: 125-129.

Vannucci, M. 1994. Ecological readings in the vedas. D.K. Print World (P) Ltd. New Delhi, p. 116.

Verma, K.S.; Agarwal, R. and Saraf, R. 1998. Aeromycology of rice field with special reference to circadian periodicity of some dominant fungal spores. In *Environmental and Aerobiology* (ed A.K. Jain), pp. 189-197, Research Periodicals and Book Publ. House, Texas.

Vesey, G. et al., (1999): Detection of specific microorganisms cultured from stratospheric air samples obtained at 41 km. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* 2018, 161 - 165.

Visez et al., (2020): Atmospheric particulate matter adhesion onto pollen: a Review. *Aerobiologia* 36, 49 - 62. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10453-019-09616-9>.

Visez et al., (2021): Biochemical composition of Phleum pratense pollen grains: A Review. *Molecular Immunology*, 136, pp 98 - 109. [10.1016/j.molimm.2021.05.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molimm.2021.05.014); hal – 03375813

Walsh, J.J. and K.A. Steidinger. (2001): Saharan dust and Florida red tides: the cyanophyte connection. *J. Geophys. Res.* 106, 1157 - 1167.

Wang et al., (2009): NADPH Oxidase activity in allergenic pollen grains of different plant species. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 387, 430 - 434.

Washington et al., (2003): Dust storm source areas determined by Ozone monitoring

- spectrometer and surface observation. *Ann. Assoc. Am. Geogr.* 93, 297 -313.
- Wei WE, Li Z, Chiew C J, et al. Presymptomatic transmission of SARS-CoV-2-Singapore. *Morb Mortal Wkly Rep* 2020; 69:411–415.
- White et al., 1999: Genome sequence of the radio - resistant bacterium *Deinococcus radiodurans* - RI. *Science*. 286, pp.1571-1577.
- William, R.H. et al. (2001): Methods for integrated air sampling and DNA analysis for detection of airborne fungal spores. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 67. 2453 - 2459.
- Winner,H.L. and R.Hurley. (1964): *Candida albicans*. Boston. Little. Brown.
- World Health Organization. Estimating mortality from COVID-19: cent6c brief. World Health Organization 2020.
- Wust, G. et al., (2003): A comparison between Anderson (AFCM) and Reuter Centrifugal Sampler (RCS - plus) for indoor sampling of airborne molds. *Aerobiologia*. 19, 125 - 148.
- Xiao et al., (2002): Transport of atmospheric impurities over the Qinghai - Xizang (Tibetan) Plateau as shown by snow chemistry. *J.Asian Earth Science*. 20, 231 - 239.
- Xu et al., (1993): A study of siliceous pnuemoconiosis in the desert area of Sunan Country, Gans Province, China. *Biomed. Environ. Science*. 6, 217 - 222.
- Yates, M.V. and S.R. Yates (1988): Modeling microbiological fate in the subsurface environment. *CRC Crit Rev. Environ. Control*. 17, 307 - 344.
- Youmans, G. et al., (1985): *The biological and clinical basis of infectious diseases*. W.B. Saunders, Philadelphia.
- Zeilinski, G.A. et al., (2000): Use of paleo - record in determining variability within volcanism - climate system. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 19 417 - 438
- Zhang et al., (2003): Sources of Asian dust and role of climate change versus desertification in Asian dust emissions. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 30, 2272.
- Zhenda, Z and W.Tao (1993): The trends of desertification and its rehabilitation in China. *Desertification Control Bull.* 22, 27 - 29.
- Zhu, J. et al., Effect of ionizing radiation on bacterial and fungal endophytes of the halophytic plant *Kalidoum schrenkianum*. *Microorganisms*. 2021; 9 (15).
<https://doi.org/10.3990/microorganisms.9051050>fur skin